

Water memory, bubble circuits and bacteria interactions

Alireza Sepehri

Independent Researcher

Abstract: Up to date, many scientific groups have investigated on the water memory and its applications in biology. The main question is that could the memory of water use in imaging and diagnosing viral/bacterial diseases? Also, could we use of memory of water in controlling bacteria and viruses? To response these questions, we have designed an experiment to use of bubble circuits within saliva in imaging and controlling microbes. Bubble circuits have several origins like: 1. Emitted waves from DNAs 2. Exchanged waves and charges between neurons within neural circuits. 3. Emitted waves from charges and ions within the blood vessels 4. Emitted waves from towers. These factors cause to the polarizations of water molecules, their motions and formation of some holes. These holes which may contain enzymes, gases and some main matters, could be surrender by several walls of polarized water molecules and ions and form bubbles. Sometimes, walls of bubbles have opposite charges and form capacitors. Also, some ions move around round walls, form some electrical currents and build round coils or inductors. On the other hand, some tubes or wires connect bubbles and play the role of resistor in a circuit. Consequently, by joining bubbles, some electrical circuits are formed. These electrical bubble circuits could exchange waves with cells, bacteria and viruses. Type of bubble circuits not only is different for males and females but also change from a time to another depending on the new interactions between cells and bacteria. To consider this theory, we can put a leaf on a slide and close it to the mouth near bubble circuits without contacting them. As previous we have argued cellular DNAs of each leaf also have their own circuits and could exchange waves with bubble circuits. These waves make transmission of bacteria from mouth to the leaf more easier. Then, we can put the leaf under a microscope and consider evolutions of bacteria. Type of interactions between bacteria and the process of formation of colony depend on the gender and are different from a person to another. Most bacteria tend to join to each other and form a wire near walls of cells. This is because that these walls have some ionic

gates and bacteria could transmit waves and ions with cells. If one blow to the leaf or close it to the moth for second time, density , current and interaction between bacteria grow. This is because that in addition to transmission of bacteria, more waves are exchanged between bubbles and leaf cells and make the best conditions for the bacterial life on the leaf. Water molecules which are transformed to the leaf, retain their memory and could help bacteria to continue their life.

Keywords: Bubble; Neuron; Saliva; Circuit; Water memory; Leaf; Microscope; Bacteria

I.Introduction

Around 30 years ago, Jacques Benveniste published a paper in Nature and argued that water has the ability to store information and retain a memory of substances previously dissolved in it even after an arbitrary number of serial dilutions [1]. Up to date, some investigators have tried to assert this idea or even use of its applications. For example, a group have assumed that waves originating from a strong pulsed electric field could transmit molecule information into water. They have tested this hypothesis experimentally on various biological systems like bacteria and plants. The results were very positive and encouraging: Both organisms reacted to an information imprint of a chosen substance [2]. Another group have obtained more wonderful result. They not only claim that bacterial/viral genetic matters could emit electromagnetic waves through the water around them but could be teleported. They have put two vessels in an inductor and apply a magnetic field to them. One vessel has included viral RNAs and water molecules and other has included only pure water. Then, they have used of PCR and other techniques and detected the signature of viral RNAs in second vessel. This means that the properties of genetic matters were transformed or teleported from one vessel to other [3-5].

Now, the question arises that if these experiments are true, could we use of water bubbles around cells to recover some information about evolutions of biological

system? Many investigations have been done on the cell-bubble interactions and their applications in biology. For example, one work has investigated the interactions that occur between bubbles formed during decompression and cells in a 3D engineered tissue phantom. In this experiment, cell death was found to significantly increase ($p=0.0116$) following a bubble-forming decompression [6]. In parallel, in many other investigations, it has been shown that bubbles could damage cell structures and prevent of the growth of cells within culture or human/animal/plant body [7-11]. However, it seems that in spite these harmful effects, bubbles could play the role of information transmitter so. For example, they may act like extracellular vesicles which contain biological matters [12]. We couldn't detect these vesicles by light microscopes easily, however, bubbles could grow and be detected by any microscope. In addition, they form some circuits which exchange information with medium and inform us from events within cells. In this research, we consider this subject. We also discuss about the interactions between bacteria and their relations with bubble circuits and water memory.

II. Bubble circuits within the saliva: Theoretical model

In this section, we propose a model which helps us to consider the origin and the role of bubble circuits in transforming information from cells to medium. In this model, bubble circuits are formed through several ways. In one way, DNAs vibrate and by their motions, their electrical charges move and some DNA currents are emerged. These currents emit some electromagnetic waves. These waves interact with charges within the cellular membranes and cause their vibrations. On the other hand, some external sources like neurons and cells could send some external fields which force into membranes and cause to their vibrations. By these vibrations, molecules of water around the cellular membranes move. By these motions, some holes are emerged and some gases like carbon dioxide, oxygen and air molecules are confined within them. In addition, maybe, some enzymes and genetic matters also be located within the holes. These holes become bigger and absorb different molecules and ions. On the walls of this hole, molecules of water and ions are moving fast and produce some electrical currents. These current emit some electromagnetic waves which carry main information of evolutions of initial cellular sources (See figure 1). In second way, neurons around the salivary glands

and interior of mouth exchange some charges and electrical signals. These signals and particles interact with water molecules, polarize them and cause to their motions. Consequently, some holes are emerged which are surrounded by polarized water molecules and some gases and matters are confined within them. These holes and matter around them form the second type of bubbles (See figure 2). In third method, bacteria interact with cells and exchange some waves with them. These waves and charges make the water molecules polarized and cause to their motions and formation of holes. These holes are surrounded by water molecules and form new bubbles (See figure 3). In fourth mechanism, ions and charges within blood vessels interact with water molecules and cause to their motions and formation of bubbles (See figure 4). And finally, sometimes, external waves like mobile waves or radio waves which are emitted by towers cause to polarization of water molecules within the mouth, their motions and emergence of holes and bubbles (See figure 5). Thus, bubbles within the mouth have different origins, however all of them are emerged by interacting between water molecules and some electromagnetic waves or electrons. From these bubbles, some big bubbles act like round coils and absorb some smaller round coils. These pairs of big and small bubbles form a neuron-like system and information, water molecules, ions and electrical charges could be exchanged between two heads of them (See figure 6). These neuron-like objects join to each other and form bubble circuits. These circuits could exchange waves with brain, heart, salivary and other cells (See figure 7). To clear this point, one can show that polarized water molecules and charges around holes within bubbles form two positive-negative walls and build some capacitors. Also, water molecules and ions move around holes and produce some round currents. These currents emit electromagnetic waves and act like coils or inductors. On the other hand, bubbles join to each other through some tubes which have resistance (See figure 8). By joining bubbles, an electrical system is formed which acts like the receiver or sender of waves (See figure 9). This circuit could exchange some electrical waves with viruses and bacteria and absorb or repel them (See figure 10).

Fig 1: The process of formation of bubbles by DNA waves

Fig 2: The process of formation of bubbles by neuron cells

Fig 3: Formations of bubbles by bacterial or viral waves

Fig 4: Formation of bubbles by blood vessels

Fig 5: Formation of bubbles by tower waves

Fig 6: A pair of bubbles form a neural like system

Fig 7: Bubble circuits in connections with neural circuits, salivary cells and other biological system within the body.

Fig 8: Comparing bubbles with electrical devices

Fig 9: Formation of bubble circuits

Fig 10: Exchanging waves between viruses, bacteria and bubble circuits

III. Bubble circuits within the saliva: Experimental Result

We have taken salivary water from different persons and put them under a light microscope. It is interesting that salivary waters have the bubble like shapes . In all of the, bubble molecules are connected to each other and form some circuits. In fact, first, big round bubbles are connected to small round bubbles by some cylindrical wire-like bubbles. Then, these pairs are connected to each other and form bubble circuits. In these circuits, light waves and water molecules move along some wire like bubbles and transform information from a big round bubble to small one or reverse. It seems that these circuits are exchanging waves with human cells and medium. In figures 11 and 12 we show the bubble circuits of a female and in figures 13 and 14, we present the bubble circuits of a male. Comparing figures, it seems that bubbles of females have more complicated shapes with

more light channels. This means that bubbles are gender dependence. This may be true. Because, the structure of bodies of males and females and specially, some of their chromosomes are different. In figure 15, we show a pair of bubbles which are connected by a tube. It is clear that water or gas molecules are transmitted from a bubble to another and transmit some biological information , enzymes and genetic matters . In figure 16, we show that in addition to biological molecules, some electromagnetic waves could be exchanged between two bubbles. These waves carry main information about their initial cellular cells and could give us the best opportunity to consider evolutions of human's body. In figure 17, one could observe that two interacting bubble rotate very fast. Each bubble is formed from air molecules, water and ions and by their motions, some electrical currents are emerged. These currents emit some electromagnetic waves which could be taken by neural network, DNAs, RNAs and other biological circuits. In figure 18, boundary wall of a bubble divide into several lines which each of them form a separate round col and emit an special wave.

Fig 11: Bubbles of a female (first photo)

Fig 12: Bubbles of a female (Second photo)

Fig 13: Bubbles of a male (first photo)

Fig 14: Bubbles of a male (Second photo)

Fig 15: Bubbles are connected by some hard and thick tubes

Fig 16: Bubbles exchange some electromagnetic waves

Fig 17: Two bubbles are rotating fast and exchange some waves

Fig 18: A closer look into walls of two interacting bubbles

IV: Water memory could determine the behavior of bacteria under different conditions

Now, the main question arises that how water memory and bubble circuits could control bacterial and viral infections. To response this question, we did some experiments. In these experiments, we have used of exchanged waves between leaf cellular circuits and bubble circuits. Previously, it has been shown that cellular DNAs have electrical circuits. Thus, DNAs within leaf cellular have some circuits. These circuits could exchange waves with bubble circuits. Exchanged waves between these circuits could have the main role in bacterial transmission from mouth to the leaf. We have put the leaf on the slide of microscope and close it to the mouth. Then, by using a microscope, we have considered the evolutions of bacteria (See figure 19). In figure 20, we present type of leaf which has been used in this experiment. In figure 21, we show bacteria which are induced by the mouth steam of a male on the liquid near the leaf corner. It seems that leaf could absorb many bacteria from a mouth. These bacteria could interact with leaf cells and each other. It seems that some electromagnetic waves are exchanged between bacteria and cells (See figure 22). Most of bacteria are located on the walls of cells. Because, cellular membranes have some channels which let them to exchange ions and electrical waves with bacteria (See figure 23). We compare these figures with figures of 24-26 which show bacterial induction by the mouth steam of a female on the leaf. Type of interactions between bacteria and cells, density of bacteria and their currents are different for males and females. This is in agreement with theory. Some chromosomes of males are different from chromosomes of females. Consequently, their waves are different and type of their interactions with bacteria is the gender dependence. This difference could be stored in the memory of water within the saliva and recovered in the liquid on the leaf. This causes that induction of bacteria on the leaf become gender dependence. If one blows on the leaf for the second time, density of bacteria grows (See figure 27). Also, the velocity of currents and interaction between bacteria increase (See figures 28 and 29). This is because that by second blowing, more interactions between bubble circuits and leaf ones occurs and more bacteria could be transmitted from the mouth to the leaf. In figures 30 and 31, we show that how mouth bacteria could join to each other and form colony on the leaf. It seems that bacteria exchange some waves with each other and invite other bacteria to join a collection. We could take exact films and videos of interaction between bacteria under the microscope and present them in near future.

Fig 19: Interaction between bacteria, bubble circuits and leaf cells

Fig 20: A leaf which could be used in our experiment

Fig 21: Bacteria which are induced by the mouth steam of a male on the leaf (leaf corner on its liquid)

Fig 22: Interaction between bacteria and leaf cells. Bacteria are induced by the mouth steam of a male on the leaf (leaf corner)

Fig 23: Interaction between bacteria and leaf cells. Bacteria are induced by the mouth steam of a male on the leaf (leaf center)

Fig 24: Bacteria which are induced by the mouth steam of a female on the leaf
(leaf corner on its liquid)

Fig 25: Interaction between bacteria and leaf cells. Bacteria are induced by the mouth steam of a female on the leaf (leaf corner)

Fig 26: Interaction between bacteria and leaf cells. Bacteria are induced by the mouth steam of a female on the leaf (leaf center)

Fig 27: Second time of blowing: Bacteria which are induced by the mouth steam of a female on the leaf (leaf corner on its liquid)

Fig 28: Current of bacteria after second blowing or closing to the mouth (a leaf corner)

Fig 29: Increasing density of bacteria on the leaf after closing to the mouth.

Fig 30: The process of formation of colony on the leaf: A. Bacteria are interacting and joining

Fig 31: The process of formation of colony on the leaf: B. Bacteria have formed colony

Conclusion:

In this research, we have considered some aspects of water memory and its application in imaging and bacterial transmission. We have shown that bubbles within the saliva have the main role in exchanging waves between human body and medium. These bubbles are formed by interaction between DNA waves, spikes between neurons, ions within the blood vessels, towers and water molecules. In fact, water molecules are polarized by electromagnetic waves, move and some holes are emerged which contain some gases and main matters. These holes are surrounded by charged walls and form the capacitors. Some ions on the walls move very fast and form round currents within the coils and inductors. These bubbles are connected through some tubes which act like some wires and resistors. By joining these electrical devices, bubble circuits are emerged which are gender dependence and could transform waves and microbes to medium. To test the model, we put a leaf on the slide and close it to the mouth. Cells of the leaf have their circuits which exchange waves and bacteria with the bubble circuits. We have put leaf under the microscope and analyze the behavior of bacteria. The interaction between bacteria and their colonies are different for males and females and are special for each person and condition. However, most bacteria could be formed wires near the wall of cells and exchange ions and waves with the cells through their ionic channels.

References:

- [1] Davenas E, Beauvais F, Amara J, Oberbaum M, Robinzon B, Miadonna A, Tedeschi A, Pomeranz B, Fortner P, Belon P, et al. Human basophil degranulation triggered by very dilute antiserum against IgE. *Nature*. 1988 Jun 30;333(6176):816-8. doi: 10.1038/333816a0. PMID: 2455231.
- [2] Igor Jerman, Romana Ružič, Rok Krašovec, Metod Škarja, Lea

Mogilnicki, “Electrical Transfer of Molecule Information into Water, Its Storage, and Bioeffects on Plants and Bacteria” *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine* Volume 24 (3),341-353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15368370500381620>.

[3] Montagnier, L.; Aïssa, J.; Ferris, S.; Montagnier, J. L.; Lavallée, C. (2009). "Electromagnetic signals are produced by aqueous nanostructures derived from bacterial DNA sequences". *Interdisciplinary Sciences: Computational Life Sciences*. 1 (2): 81–90. doi:10.1007/s12539-009-0036-7. PMID 20640822.

[4] *Montagnier, Luc; Del Giudice, Emilio; Aïssa, Jamal; Lavallee, Claude; Motschwiller, Steven; Capolupo, Antonio; Polcari, Albino; Romano, Paola; Tedeschi, Alberto; Vitiello, Giuseppe (2015). "Transduction of DNA information through water and electromagnetic waves". *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*. 34 (2): 106–112. arXiv:1501.01620*

[5] *Montagnier, L.; Aïssa, J.; Giudice, E. Del; Lavallee, C.; Tedeschi, A.; Vitiello, G. (8 July 2011). "DNA waves and water". *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 306 (1): 012007. arXiv:1012.5166.*

[6] Walsh, C., Ovenden, N., Stride, E. *et al.* Quantification of cell-bubble interactions in a 3D engineered tissue phantom. *Sci Rep* **7**, 6331 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-06678-y>.

[7] Matzke, Edwin B. “The Three-Dimensional Shape of Bubbles in Foam-An Analysis of the Role of Surface Forces in Three-Dimensional Cell Shape Determination.” *American Journal of Botany*, vol. 33, no. 1, 1946, pp. 58–80. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/2437492. Accessed 22 Jan. 2021.

[8] Chalmers, J.J. Cells and bubbles in sparged bioreactors. *Cytotechnology* **15**, 311–320 (1994). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00762406>.

[9] Wu J. Mechanisms of animal cell damage associated with gas bubbles and cell protection by medium additives. *J Biotechnol.* 1995 Dec 1;43(2):81-94. doi: 10.1016/0168-1656(95)00133-7. PMID: 8562021.

[10] Jean St-Pierre, Anthony A. Wragg, Behaviour of electrogenerated hydrogen and oxygen bubbles in narrow gap cells—part II. Application in chlorine production, *Electrochimica Acta*, Volume 38, Issue 13, 1993, Pages 1705-1710, ISSN 0013-4686, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4686\(93\)85065-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4686(93)85065-7).

[11] Walls, P.L.L., McRae, O., Natarajan, V. *et al.* Quantifying the potential for bursting bubbles to damage suspended cells. *Sci Rep* **7**, 15102 (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-14531-5>.

[12] Chiabotto G, Gai C, Deregibus MC, Camussi G. Salivary Extracellular Vesicle-Associated exRNA as Cancer Biomarker. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2019;11(7):891. Published 2019 Jun 26. doi:10.3390/cancers11070891